

Building Corporate Sustainable Framework Based on Swastika Philosophy

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Abstract

Aims this research was aimed at formulating the swastika's values as the guideline in harmonizing stakeholders' interest and implementing it in the corporate's sustainable framework.

Approach This was qualitative design research that used a phenomenology approach. The researchers had interviewed Hindu's common people, scholars, and priests who apply Swastika in their daily lives, and also 2 directors of state-owned companies in East Java about the implementation of stakeholders' engagement.

Findings The interviews revealed that there were values of balance, harmony, innovation, and sustainability in the Swastika. Besides, the researchers also found the stakeholders' grouping models which were based on the vertical-horizontal relationship as shown in the Swastika symbol that can be used as a reference in developing the sustainable corporate framework. The interviews with the directors revealed that the strategy of engaging the stakeholders should be based on the harmony of interests of all stakeholders.

Practical Implications The findings could give reference to sustainability practitioners to develop corporates sustainable frameworks.

Originality/Value The values of balances, harmonies, innovations and sustainability, and stakeholders grouping in Swastika were newly found values from its believers with relevancy in developing the sustainable corporate framework.

Keywords: Swastika, framework, stakeholders' harmony, and Sustainability

1. Introduction

Integrating three sustainable dimensions – social life, the environment, and economy – by balancing/harmonizing the creation of values for stakeholders' interests, including the environment and society in all level business activities, is a holistic corporate sustainable approach (Bocken et al, 2015). To ensure the investors, employees, customers, and suppliers, a company has to keep a positive relationship with all groups of stakeholders, which can be the source of competitive predominance (Susniene, and Vargas, 2005)

Sustainability management should belong to the company's ever-improving strategy and innovation. Sustainable strategy is based on the engagement of stakeholders to collaborate to improve each value. "The main purpose of the corporation is improving the values of the shareholders, and this cannot be well achieved if other stakeholders' interests are not managed well" (Day Report, 1994). Ignoring certain

stakeholders can give unbeneficial effect for the organization as losing good employees, loyal customers, qualified suppliers, and capital withdrawal or shareholders' support which in the long run will lead to the decline in the image of the company and in financial situation (Ramona Florea, 2013)

Instituting sustainability and integrating it in the company's competitive predominant strategy need a sustainable framework as a reference in the planning, implementation, control, and evaluation of the sustainable program. To be able to give a good reference, a sustainable framework should be developed from the values of balance, harmony, innovation, and sustainability.

Swastika possesses a meaning of luck, prosperity, and safety for its believers. The vertical-horizontal lines/bars give a clue to the believers that harmonious relationships both vertically up (God) and down (human being) is the source of happiness (luck, prosperity, and safety). It is said that to experience happiness, the

human being as the center of life in this world, should be able to harmonize his/her relationship vertically and horizontally. Besides the vertical-horizontal relationship and the direction of the Swastika rotation depict the values of balance, harmony, innovation, and sustainability.

The harmonious relationship among various sides exists in many sectors and levels of life, whether it is in the family, society, organization, and corporation. Each structured relationship on any level can be understood as a vertical-horizontal relationship. The meaning of this universal relationship will always exist in every organization since there are always bosses, subordinates, and colleagues. The design of vertical-horizontal relationships in Swastika which is described in the values of balance, harmony, creation, and innovation is the important values that should be developed and always be improved to gain corporate's sustainability. Applying those values in the corporate's sustainable framework should be prioritized since these will be the basic achievement for every corporate's sustainability.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Sustainability Management Accountancy

Management accountant has an important decisive role in the achievement of corporate sustainability. The practice of management accountancy is the arrangement that institutionalizes the framework in which members of the organization negotiate the strategy, the budget, and decide the work's targets (Berry et al, 2007). Furthermore, Burnett and Hansen (2008) described that a management accountant is the facilitator of the decision maker in an organization. Management accountant has to put the issue of sustainability into the facilitating process so that the organization can make a decision towards sustainable development (Albelda, 2011).

The expansion of this role requires the management accountant to know more about the whole business (including business model) and the operating environment in order that he/she knows the risks and the chance the organization has. Management accountancy

which is a process of identifying, measuring, accumulating, analyzing, interpreting, and communicating information (CIMA, 2011) intend to give relevant information to the managers during the process of planning, evaluating, controlling, and decision-making (Bartolomeo et al., 2000)

Mistry, Low & Sharma (2012) identified some stimulants to put in sustainable development into accountancy practices. The two related stimulants are cost saving and risk management. Social and environmental fairness cannot be separated from economic feasibility. Therefore, it is important that the management accountant and a manager take sustainability into account as an integral part of their decision-making (Gould, 2011). The corporate should be innovative and sensitive towards the environment, and able to integrate the environment information into its business strategy in order to improve the environment performance while enjoying the benefit of the economy. For this purpose, a company needs to possess a right information system that is able to integrate all the relevant information and to provide that information to be used by the manager to make a decision (Jayanthi, 2012).

The overpressure on the measurement of monetary, conventional financial accounting, in relation to the ecological impact of an organization, causes the predicted chances and risks incomplete. Information on the physical and qualitative environment will be important when it is time to assess ecological damage that cannot be restored or when a company's activities are beyond the supportive resources (Schaltegger & Buritt, 2000, pp 77). The adoption of a strategic approach means that strategic management accounting emphasizes steps in which an organization has to adapt its resources with the market demand, especially with competitive pressure, to reach the predetermined organization's aims. Empirical evidence indicates that management accountancy is regarded to establish and be established by a

company's strategies and/or business (Kober et al., 2007; Langfield-Smith, 1997)

Sustainable accountancy explains part of the accountancy which involves activity, method, and system to record, analyze, and report :

1. The financial impact caused by society and the environment
2. The ecological and social impact from the decided economic system
3. More importantly, the interaction and involvement of socio-, environmental and economic problems which are the true three sustainable dimensions

This definition of sustainable accounting helps to answer its role in corporate responsibility management as discussed by McKernan (2007).

2.2.Sustainability

The corporate's operational procedure has to maintain the preservation of both environmental and social life in obtaining benefits as it was planned before and as its commitment to preserving the resources so that the future generation needs can be fulfilled. As explained by Rachel (2015) the aim of the whole sustainable development is the long term economic and environmental stabilities which can only be achieved through the integration and the acknowledgement of economic, environmental, and social problems during the process of decision-making.

Neubaum & Zahra (2006) defined corporate sustainability as the ability of the company to maintain and support its growth from time to time effectively to fulfill the expectation of each stakeholder. Corporate sustainability bases its success on its ability to fulfill the needs of the stakeholders.

Sustainable development means adopting strategies and business activities to fulfill the present corporate's needs and its stakeholders as well as to protect, maintain, and improve human and natural resources that are needed in the future. International Institute for Sustainable Development (1992) in its publication, mentioned seven needed steps to manage a company in accordance with

sustainable development principles which involves :

- a. Analyzing the stakeholders' needs
- b. Setting the policies and the aims of sustainable development
- c. Designing and carrying out the implementation plans
- d. Developing the company's supportive culture
- e. Developing working measurement and standard
- f. Preparing reports
- g. Enhancing internal supervisory process

A sustainable society cannot be achieved if every individual or group is concerned with its own sake. The decision making of sustainability involves assessment and consideration of ethical social analysis, economy, and ethics to inform and take into account every form of assessment including human welfare, cultural values, and human values (IPCC, 2014). Peters (1997) explicitly reported that he supported the idea of a good balance between investors' and stakeholders' needs.

Gladwin et al (1995) in his article: Shifting paradigm for sustainable development emphasized that sustainability is the process of achieving human development inclusively, connectedly, fairly, wisely, and safely. The components of sustainable development are: i) inclusiveness (human and environmental system, near and far, present and future), ii) connectivity (the problems of the world which are interconnected and interdependent), iii) equity (distribution of resources and properties' rights evenly), iv) prudence (maintenance and prevention), and v) security (safety from chronic threats). In operation, a corporate's sustainable achievement is guided by sustainable principles. Timothy C. Lindsey (2011) presented 3 major sustainable principles which consist of:

1. sustainable enhancement can be achieved by the reduction of waste
2. the quality enhancement will lead to sustainable enhancement
3. sustainability can be well achieved by the implementation of a better system

Faez Saad Al-Shihri (2013) grouped sustainable principles in accordance with environmental, economic, and social categories, which form sustainable performance as follows:

1) Environmental Performances

- a. Maintaining environmental qualities – clean water, air, and soil
- b. Preserving the natural ecosystem
- c. Planning the use of sustainable land to reduce the overuse land and promoting the smart growth
- d. Reducing pollution and degraded the environment

2) Economic Performances

- a. Conserving the natural resources: land, water, air, fauna, flora, mineral, etc
- b. Reusing and recycling materials
- c. Expanding economic opportunities: green economy, the use of local natural resources
- d. Having healthy policies and economic rules

3) Social Performances

- a. Equity in distributing resources and works
- b. Public transportations' sound
- c. Affordable housing for every income group
- d. Well public participation: engaging all stakeholders in decision making
- e. Health and public safety
- f. Qualified education and public awareness on sustainability
- g. Care for the needy: the poor, the handicapped, the minority

2.3. Stakeholder

The best interdependent relationships with all parties involved rely on and trust others to do what is necessary to benefit the overall relationship. They represent the classic opportunities to be mutually beneficial for business (Barney, 2001). Stakeholders' perspective reveals that a company exists not only for the shareholders' interests but also for the employees, suppliers, customers, and in a certain limit, for society's interest (Eusep Daniel, 2004). Managers should serve all

stakeholders' interests and care for all partner's value chains (Freeman, 1983).

Stakeholders are those who possess rights or interests in an ecosystem (Mayers, 2005). For an organization, stakeholders are groups or individuals who are capable of influencing or be influenced by the organization's goal achievement. Stakeholders can be individuals, communities, social communities, or organizations. All individuals or groups, if their interests are valid and which based on the stakeholders' interests strength analysis show legitimation, should be included in the policy making and implementation which influence their position in the organization.

Based on the position in the organization, Florea RM grouped the stakeholders into internal and external stakeholders (Florea RM, 2007). Friedman & Miles (2006) identified three stakeholder categories based on how they are influenced by the decision or any company's actions. They are Primary Stakeholders, Secondary Stakeholders, and Key Stakeholders. Primary stakeholders are individuals or groups which are positively or negatively directly affected by the strategies, decisions, or actions of the company. The decision, usually at the same time, positively and negatively affect other groups. Employees' raise, for example, positively affect the employee's interest but negatively affect the shareholders. Secondary stakeholders are individuals or groups which are indirectly affected, either positively or negatively, by the company's decisions or actions. Key stakeholders are individuals or organizations which may possess either one of the two first groups. Key stakeholders play important roles in decision making and also in its implementation because they are involved in the company's management or finance. They are policymakers, officials, important professionals, or people who have position and strong influence.

Developing a mutually beneficial relationship with all stakeholders needs an adequate understanding of the stakeholders. A company needs to do a mapping of its

stakeholders. The mapping is a collaboration process on researches, debates, and discussions that are taken from all perspectives to decide key stakeholders' interests list in all stakeholders spectrum. The mapping involves four phases (BSR, 2011):

1. Identifying: list of relevant groups, organizations, and people
2. Analyzing: understanding the perspective and interest of the stakeholders
3. Mapping: visualizing the relationship between the aims and other stakeholders
4. Prioritizing: deciding the stakeholders level of relevancy and identifying problems

The process of mapping stakeholders has equal importance with its result. And the quality of that process depends on the knowledge of the people who participate in it.

The analysis of stakeholders' strength is an organized approach to assess the support level or challenge from concerned parties and to predict how they will react if there are changes. This is an approach to understand a system by identifying the main actors or stakeholders and assess each interest, or its impact in the system (James Mayers, 2005). The involvement level is the main factor that decides the most relevant methods.

International Analysis Spectrum for Public Participation (IASP2) (2007) proposed five kinds of involvement which can be evaluated as follows:

- a. Informing: give balance and objective information to stakeholders
- b. Consulting: find perspective and input from stakeholders; acquire their feedback on the analysis, alternatives, or decision of the key steps of the evaluation process
- c. Involving: work with the stakeholders in all processes to make sure that their concerns and perspectives are understood and took into account consistently
- d. Collaborating: be the partner with stakeholders to make decisions during the evaluation process (developing alternatives and position identification or favorable point of action). Collaboration indicates shared ownership between organization

and stakeholders, and requires a bigger decision-making level

- e. Empowering: stakeholders share the responsibility to make a decision and be responsible for the result of the decision.

2.4.Swastika

The symbol and its interpretation are two inseparable things in human's lives. Each symbol has its own meaning depending on the interpretation given by the subject who judges it. This means that a symbol can mean the same or different and even have the opposite meaning, depending on the experience of the subject towards that symbol. The swastika is one symbol. It can mean differently for some social groups.

Researches which had been done in some parts of the world showed that swastika was a widely spread symbol and used by some society groups. In some big human civilization, the swastika was a special symbol that gave prosperity, wealth as well as glory. This can be found in Sloka Weda:

Swasti na indro vruddhastravaha
Svastianah pasha vishvavedaha!
Swasti natakshya arishtanemihi
Svatino bruhaspatirdadhatu

May God the Almighty possesses an unending glory which will be beneficial for us

May all rulers of the universe will give benefit to us

May the strong protection from the universe give us luck

May God the Highest existence give benefit to us

(RegWeda, I.89.6;
Sayanaacarya, 2016)

In Hindu's civilization, Swastika is a symbol that cannot be separated from the daily spiritual-religious practices. Swastika indicates luck, prosperity, and other virtues. In other words, the swastika has positive meanings. We can find this symbol everywhere in India.

The swastika is formed by an intersection of two perpendicular lines/bars with exactly the same length in a clockwise direction. There are many varieties of this symbol in accordance with the time and its users. But the oldest symbol is as presented in picture 1. And it is used in Hindu. In Indonesia the symbol is used in the Hindu Dharma Council of Indonesia (IHCI), the highest assembly of the Hindus. It is presented in the following picture.

figure 1 : Swastika, Symbol of Hindu Dharma Council of Indonesia

Sources : Hindu Dharma Council of Indonesia

The use of this symbol for the Hindus in Indonesia involves the prayer of safety. The symbol can be found in houses, places of worship, paintings, and properties for Hindus' ceremonies. By setting up this symbol on the wall, the hosts wish God will give them protection, safety, and luck to all the residents of the house.

The four sides of swastika describe many different things and possess a deep philosophy. As in Hindus' philosophy, the four sides of the symbol are the four sides of Veda which are the four pillars in Hinduism: i). Rigveda, ii). Samaveda, iii). Yajurveda, and iv). Atharvaveda. The sides also describe the four stages of human life: i). Brahmacharya – the stage of learning (being a pupil), ii). Grihastha – the stage of settling down (marriage life), iii). Vanaprastha – stage of leaving the attachment to this world, and iv). Sanyasa – stage of devoting oneself to the spiritualism. Furthermore, the sides

describe the four purposes of life: Dharma, Artha, Kama, and Moksha.

Swastika in Hindus' philosophy is a symbol that brings success in all aspects of life through balance and harmony of vertical-horizontal relationship which is portrayed by the four arms.

Swastika which represents an interaction between horizontal and vertical dialectics (Sharma, 2003) is a diagram of four forces: i). market force. ii). Nation force. iii). Earth/Nature force, and iv). Spiritual force. If the forces are in harmony, there will be a synergy. On the other hand, if they are not in harmony, there will be chaos (Sharma, 2017). Sharma used this swastika model to describe the interaction of four globalization forces and proposed the Swastika Model and Literary New Earth for the sustainable vision which balances aspects of market – nation – earth – spiritual in developing humans toward sustainability. The vertical-horizontal relationship is the relationship which always exists among the doer and other higher parties, and lower parties, and parties of the same level. This symbol inspires its believers that success, happiness, and prosperity can be achieved from the balance and harmony of the vertical – horizontal relationship they have done in all aspects of life. The clockwise rotation symbolizes the rotation of the universe or the process of creation in which in every creation there are innovations.

Swastika as a sustainable symbol is also associated with the coherence on the five principles of sustainability core which involve (i) spiritual domain (orientation attitude and basic universal code of conduct), (ii) social domain (the relationship of culture and social), (iii) domain of life (better attitude), (iv) economic domain (luck), and (v) material domain (regulating the flow of energy) (Ben-Eli, 2005). A global exploration of Swastika in every culture can reveal a hidden pattern of works and matrix of civilization. The Swastika works in every level of deep abstraction of cosmology and ecology which is only open

for introspective contemplative mind (Sandhi, 2016, 07).

3. Research methodology

By using the phenomenology approach, the researchers had thorough interviews with two participant groups. The first group experienced the use of swastika themselves. These participants consisted of two categories, i.e. common people and scholars/clergymen. The researchers interviewed 13 participants, questioning about:

- a. The common use and the benefits expected from the use of the symbol
- b. The meaning of the symbol
- c. The values contained and the implementation in corporate's sustainability
- d. The relationship that exists from the vertical – horizontal lines/bars philosophy and how that relationship provides guidelines of harmonization of interest in the involvement of stakeholders.

The participants of the second group were those who had experiences in a corporate's sustainability practices. They were directors. The researchers interviewed two directors of two state-owned companies which headquarter in East Java. They were asked: i) the aim of corporate sustainability. ii) stakeholders' mapping and identification of their interests, iii) how the stakeholders influence and be influenced by the corporate's policies, and iv) the strategies of harmonizing the interests because of the stakeholders' involvement.

4. Discussion

1. Stakeholders' grouping based on Swastika Philosophy

Swastika in a sustainable context classifies the stakeholders into 3 groups:

- a. The stakeholder's group which is positioned above the center point of the symbol has a vertical relationship (up) since it is based on a relationship of power. This group is usually of rules and policies

maker whose policies should be carried out by directors. This stakeholder group consists of shareholders and the government.

- b. The stakeholder group is positioned below the center point. It has a vertical relationship (down) which is based on an empowered and protection relationship. This consists of any parties which have (positive/negative) impacts on the corporate's operation. The corporate has a responsibility to preserve the nature, social and cultural orders in which the company operates. These stakeholders consist of the environments (nature, social and culture). Environment preservation can be in the corporate's sustainability support.
- c. The stakeholder group is in parallel with the center point of the symbol. This has a horizontal relationship which is based on a mutually beneficial partnership. The contribution given by one party depends on the contribution accepted from other parties whether it gives financial or non-financial benefit. A company has a mutually and inter-dependable relationship with some affecting parties. This symbiotic mutualism relationship is like a harmonic relationship among human which can give happiness as described on the horizontal line of Swastika. This group consists of customers, employees, creditors, and suppliers. Figure 2, presents the grouping of stakeholders in accordance with the Swastika concept.

Managers should serve all stakeholders' interests (shareholders, employees, creditors, customers, and society) and care about the value chain partners (Freeman, R.E. and Reed, D.L., 1983)

Figure 2. Stakeholder grouping based on Swastika Philosophy

Sources : researcher construction result

Just like a wheel, the center point of Swastika should be strong, be able to harmonize and support the spokes to create a balanced rotation in its process of creation. Mitchell et al. (1997) identified stakeholders as any parties which possess power, legitimation and urgency towards the existence of a corporate. Furthermore, Florea R.M (2007) grouped shareholders and employees as internal stakeholders; customers, suppliers, business partners, communities, society as external stakeholders

A director who manages a company serves all stakeholders' interests. As it has been described in Swastika, the director is the center point of the rotation. He has to have a strong commitment to satisfying the stakeholders. This strong commitment is elaborated in the policies and sustainable strategies that are integrated into a company's competitive excellence strategies. For many companies, stakeholders' relationship offers very big potency. For some, that relationship can even be the source of competitive excellence (Dalia Susniene, Povilas Vanagas, 2005).

2. Harmonizing Stakeholders' interests based on Swastika Philosophy

Swastika guidelines in harmonizing stakeholders' interests should have:

- a. Management as the company's wheel player (the center point of Swastika) should be strong, which is characterized by

possessing aims, policies, and success strategies.

- b. The policies and stakeholders' harmony program should be supported by stakeholder mapping which can give an overall description of their existence, influence, power, and interests on the company's existence. Stakeholder management is a process of analyzing and harmonizing interests to identify the most sustainable solution to develop a long term company. This is also a communication process that enables people to have a consultation, give information, and explain the stakeholders the strategy which will be implemented and also its implication (Ramona Florea, 2013). From the perspective of total quality management, there are three different concepts of how to fulfill the different stakeholders' interests: accommodating, aligning, and balancing the interests (Dalia Susniene, Povilas Vanagas, 2005). Figure 3 presents how the swastika works which can give guidelines in sustainable governance.

Figure 3. Harmonizing Stakeholders' interests based on Swastika Philosophy

Sources : researcher construction result

The Swastika Role

1. The center point (management) should be strong in maintaining the balance and harmony of its relationship with all spokes/lines/bars (stakeholders) in the rotation of Swastika (company operations).
2. Each swastika spoke represents the interest of the stakeholders that need to be fulfilled. Management should be able to harmonize all the interests of the stakeholders in the engagement strategy, so as to be able to meet the interests of all stakeholders proportionally.
3. The clockwise rotation is the process of creating (innovation) values for the company and all its stakeholders.
4. Sustainability will be achieved if the center point is able to harmonize the vertical – horizontal relationship and maximize the values (benefit) of all stakeholders.

3. Sustainable Framework based on Swastika Philosophy

Representation of the built essence represents participants' experiences on the phenomena faced both by swastika believers and sustainable practitioners. Those essences are the source for the researchers in developing a sustainable framework based on swastika philosophy. Based on the built essence, a company's sustainability should have the following criteria:

- a. A corporate sustainability should be able to give prosperity (benefit/value) to all stakeholders as in the meaning of swastika: good deeds, safety, and prosperity under the protection of God.
- b. A corporate sustainability should be based on innovation in creating values, strategy balance, and resources support as well as material and spiritual aims as what is meant by the swastika symbol.
- c. Sustainable policies and strategies should precisely identify the company's stakeholders in the stakeholder map so that programs of involvement can give maximum benefits both for the company and the stakeholders. Based on the

relationship in the swastika, directors manage the interests of three groups of stakeholder as explained in point 4.1. a company's sustainable policies and strategies should be supported by policies and the harmony of stakeholders' interests strategies. To be able to harmonize the interests (essence 4 & 5):

1. Management as the company's wheel player (the center point of the swastika) should be strong to be able to manage the rhythm of the play (involvement) of stakeholders (the stokes of the swastika) in the company sustainability.
2. Every stakeholder (the stokes) has a proportional role and interest and obtain a benefit in the relationship with the company.
3. A company should possess stakeholders' ma, which can give a description of their existence in a sustainable company.
4. The policy of involving stakeholders should be integrated with the sustainable company's strategies as its source of management strength.

The above-mentioned criteria are stated in the following sustainable company's framework:

1. Company's vision and mission
2. Sustainable aims
3. Identifying stakeholders and their interests
4. Harmonizing the interests in policies and strategies to involve stakeholders
5. Planning and innovation programs
6. Implementing sustainable programs
7. Evaluation
8. Report

Figure 4. Sustainable Framework based on Swastika Philosophy

Sources : researcher construction result

1. Company's vision and mission

It tells the company's vision and mission. Vision discusses what is needed by the company in the future and the level it wants to reach. Vision is a communication of future dreams a company wants (Ozden, 2011). A strong vision helps a business to predict events in the future, prepares changes and innovations, encourages the business to face the future, estimates changes in customers' demand, and enhancing employees' efficiency (Powers, 2012). Whereas mission is the steps on how the company should take to reach the vision. Cornelissen (2004) used the perspective of stakeholders' values to explain that: "A mission is a general expression of an organization's aim that, ideally, is in line with the organization's scope and limitation.

2. Sustainable aims

A company's sustainable aims are to make its stakeholders prosperous. Prosperity represents the ability to create values for all stakeholders. The higher the values of the stakeholders the better the achievement level of a company's sustainable aims.

3. Identifying stakeholders and their interests

Identifying stakeholders and their interests toward the existence of a company should be performed and set out in stakeholders' map. Swastika classifies stakeholders into three categories: i) Stakeholders positioned above the center, with whom the management has an upward vertical relationship, possess a superior position, a strong power and a command line to the management. This upward vertical line represents the relationship with the shareholders, who are considered as the founders/owners of a company. ii) This category, horizontally positioned at the same level as the center point of the swastika, is related to the management based on common interests. Its relationship is of a mutualistic symbiosis which creates a mutually beneficial contract between stakeholders and company. This horizontal relationship can be identified in the relationship between the management and the employees, suppliers, customers, and other parallel parties. iii) This group of stakeholders is positioned below the swastika center point, where the company performs its functions of protection and empowers to maintain its existence. This downward vertical line represents the management's relationship with its both natural and social environments.

4. Harmonizing the interests in stakeholder engagement policies and strategies

Companies should harmonize various stakeholders' interests in their engagement policy and strategy in order to maximize the benefits gained by both the company and the stakeholders.

5. Planning and innovation programs

Sustainability is achieved through overall efficiency in utilizing economic resources. For that reason, innovation plays an important role in a company's sustainability strategy. There will be no sustainability without innovation, and likewise there will be no innovation without sustainability. Companies should have an innovation roadmap in their sustainability policy and strategy.

6. Implementing sustainable programs

These programs are integrated into stakeholder engagement. The management (in swastika center point), who is in charge of keeping the wheels of business turning, should be powerful in order to be able to maintain the rhythm (engagement) of the stakeholders (swastika spoke/foot) in company sustainability. Each stakeholder (swastika spoke/foot) has its own proportional roles and interests, gives contributions, and gains benefits in his relation with the company. In this perspective, the management's strength is reflected in its commitment, policy, and capability in integrating all potentials (including the stakeholders') in the company sustainability program.

7. Evaluation

Feedback from the performance of the sustainability program serves as material for improving the company's sustainability. For that reason, in order to identify the adequacy and novelty of sustainability policy and program, periodic evaluation is inevitable in a sustainable framework. The company should conduct evaluation periodically for all sustainable activities and announce the evaluation results as feedback for all related parties.

8. Report

The last part of managing sustainability is giving a report. GRI Standard has provided guidelines for making a sustainability report. The 3 areas of performance to be reported are economic, social, and environmental performances.

5. Conclusion

1. The vertical-horizontal relationship in swastika gives a guideline to managing stakeholders' interests. Swastika classifies stakeholders, based on their relationship with the company, into 3 major categories:
 - a. These stakeholders, positioned above the Swastika center point, are connected by an upward vertical line that is based on power relations. Typically, as shareholders and government officials, these stakeholders make rules and policies to be implemented by directors, who are in charge of a company.
 - b. These stakeholders, positioned below the Swastika center point, are connected by a downward vertical line that is based on an empowerment and protection relationship. They consist of those parties affected (positively/negatively) by the company's business operation. The company is obliged to preserve nature as well as both the social and cultural order of the location where the company operates. These stakeholders consist of the environment (the nature, society, and culture). The environmental preservation of the surroundings can support the company's sustainability.
 - c. These stakeholders, positioned at the same level as the Swastika center point, are connected by a horizontal line that is based on mutual partnership relationships. The company has a mutually interdependent relationship with other parties, and each party's existence can influence one another. Mutualistic symbiosis occurring in this kind of relationship, which is

analogous to the harmonious relationship among human beings, is reflected by the swastika horizontal line. This group of stakeholders that is connected by this horizontal line consists of customers, employees, creditors, and suppliers.

2. The sustainability framework is set up by initially establishing its criteria based on essentials developed in this research. The researcher has developed 5 essentials that have become criteria of sustainability:
 - a. Company sustainability should be able to provide prosperity (benefits/values) to all stakeholders, reflecting the word swastika which means good deeds, safety, and prosperity under the protection of God.(essential 1)
 - b. Company sustainability should be set up based on innovation in the creation of value, the balance of strategy and resource support, as well as material and spiritual goals that reflect the symbol of Swastika. (essential2)
 - c. Policy and strategy of sustainability should be able to identify a company's stakeholders accurately in a stakeholder map so that the engagement program can provide maximal benefit for both the company and its stakeholders. Based on connection lines in Swastika, the management (directors) manages the interests of the 3 stakeholder groups: i) Stakeholders belonging to the position above the center point to whom the management has an upward vertical connection. This group of stakeholders has a superior position, a high power, and a command line to the management. This upward vertical relation is described as a relation with the shareholders who are the founder (owner) of the company. ii) Stakeholders positioned at the same level as the Swastika center point (horizontal line) that is connected to the management based on common

interest. The management's relationship with this group is of mutualistic symbiosis, from which mutual work contracts are signed between the stakeholders and the company. This horizontal line connection can be seen from the company's relationship with its employees, suppliers, and other equal parties. iii) Stakeholders positioned below the Swastika center point to whom the company performs its empowering function in order to maintain its existence. This downward vertical line is the company's relationship with both the natural and social environment. (Essential 3)

- d. The company's sustainability should be built based on the values of balance, innovation, harmony and power. (Essential 2)
- e. The company's sustainability policy and strategy should be supported by stakeholders' interest in harmonization policy and strategy in order to harmonize its stakeholders' interests. (Essentials 4 and 5):
 1. Management, who is in charge of keeping the wheel of business turning (Swastika center point), should be strong in order to be able to maintain the rhythm of the turning (engagement) of the stakeholders (Swastika spoke) in the company's sustainability.
 2. Each stakeholder (Swastika spoke) possesses his/her own proportional role and interest, contributes, benefits in his/her relationship with the company.
 3. The company should have a stakeholder map that can describe its existence in the company's sustainability.
 4. The policy of stakeholder's engagement should be integrated with the company's sustainability as a source of management strength.

Those criteria are set out in the company's sustainability framework as follows:

1. Company's vision and mission
2. Sustainable aims
3. Identifying stakeholders and their interests
4. Harmonizing the interests in policies and strategies to involve stakeholders
5. Planning and innovation programs
6. Implementing sustainable programs
7. Evaluation
8. Report

There are 3 novelties discovered in this research, which include:

1. Classifying stakeholders based Swastika vertical-horizontal relationship into:
 - a. Stakeholders whose position is above the Swastika center point. This constitutes an upward vertical relationship.
 - b. Stakeholders whose position is below the Swastika center point. This constitutes a downward vertical relationship.
 - c. Stakeholders whose position is at the same level as the Swastika center point. This constitutes a horizontal relationship.
2. Guidelines to harmonizing stakeholder's interests in the company's sustainability based on Swastika method can be followed as follows:
 - a. Center point (management) should have strength in maintaining balance and harmony in its connection to all spokes (stakeholders) in Swastika's rotation (Company's business operation)
 - b. Each spoke of Swastika represents stakeholders' interests that need to be fulfilled. Management should be able to harmonize all of the stakeholders' interests in its engagement strategy in order to be able to fulfill all of those stakeholders' interests proportionally.

- c. Swastika's clockwise rotation constitutes a value creation process (innovation) for both the company and the stakeholders.
3. Company's sustainable framework that is built based on Swastika philosophy consists of:
 - a. Company's vision and mission
 - b. Sustainable aims
 - c. Identifying stakeholders and their interests
 - d. Harmonizing the interests in policies and strategies to engage stakeholders
 - e. Planning and innovation programs
 - f. Implementing sustainable programs
 - g. Evaluation
 - h. Report

Research Limitation

This research merely developed the Company Sustainable Framework based on Swastika philosophy through developing the essentials of phenomena experienced by the participants, both Swastika believers and sustainability practitioners. Since this research has yet to dig more deeply into formulizing stakeholders' values as the company's sustainability builders, the strategy to maximize stakeholders' values in the company's sustainability has yet to be formulized either. These 2 things can be interesting topics for the next researchers to dig more deeply into the company's sustainability.

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